

The macro loop

Harald Schröder

A circle comparable to the earth's sphere (planet's sphere) can be called a macro loop.

R_2 = radius of the macro loop

R_p = radius of the planet

$R_1 = R_p + h$

h = height of the loop over the planet's surface to the deepest point

K = gravitation

Z = centrifugal force

m_p = mass of the planet

m = mass of the small ball in the loop

G = gravitational constant

The distance - important for the gravitation - can be described as:

$$r^2 = (R_1 + R_2)^2 + R_2^2 - 2 \cdot (R_1 + R_2) \cdot R_2 \cos(180^\circ - \gamma)$$

We get the following expression of gravitation:

$$K = \frac{Gm_p m}{r^2}$$
$$= \frac{Gm_p m}{(R_1 + R_2)^2 + R_2^2 - 2 \cdot (R_1 + R_2) \cdot R_2 \cos(180^\circ - \gamma)}$$

Centrifugal force:

$$Z = \frac{mv^2}{R_2}$$

with velocity of the ball v .

cosine law (see fig.):

$$(R_1 + R_2)^2 = R_2^2 + r^2 - 2R_2 r \cos \beta$$

Transformation:

$$\cos \beta = \frac{R_2^2 + r^2 - (R_1 + R_2)^2}{2R_2 r}$$

r inserted: $\cos(180^\circ - \gamma) = -\cos \gamma$

$$\cos \beta = \frac{2R_2^2 - 2 \cdot (R_1 + R_2) \cdot R_2 \cos(180^\circ - \gamma)}{2R_2 r}$$

$$= \frac{R_2 + (R_1 + R_2) \cdot \cos \gamma}{\sqrt{(R_1 + R_2)^2 + R_2^2 + 2 \cdot (R_1 + R_2) \cdot R_2 \cos \gamma}}$$

We transform the denominator:

$$\begin{aligned} & (R_1 + R_2)^2 + R_2^2 + 2 \cdot (R_1 + R_2) \cdot R_2 \cos \gamma \\ &= R_1^2 + 2R_1R_2 + R_2^2 + R_2^2 + (2R_1R_2 + 2R_2^2) \cdot \cos \gamma \\ &= 2R_1R_2 \cdot (1 + \cos \gamma) + R_1^2 + 2R_2^2 \cdot (1 + \cos \gamma) \\ &= R_1^2 + 2 \cdot (R_1R_2 + R_2^2) \cdot (1 + \cos \gamma) \\ &= R_1^2 + 2R_2 \cdot (R_1 + R_2) \cdot (1 + \cos \gamma) \end{aligned}$$

We view the figure:

With the figure we see:

$$\cos \beta = \frac{Z}{K}$$

We insert for Z and K and we equate this with another expression of $\cos \beta$:

$$\frac{v_{min}^2 \cdot (R_1^2 + 2R_2 \cdot (1 + \cos \gamma) \cdot (R_1 + R_2))}{Gm_p R_2} = \cos \beta = \frac{R_2 + (R_1 + R_2) \cdot \cos \gamma}{\sqrt{R_1^2 + 2R_2 \cdot (1 + \cos \gamma) \cdot (R_1 + R_2)}}$$

With the transformation, we obtain an expression of the macro loop's minimum velocity:

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{\frac{Gm_p R_2 \cdot (R_2 + (R_1 + R_2) \cdot \cos \gamma)}{(R_1^2 + 2R_2 \cdot (1 + \cos \gamma) \cdot (R_1 + R_2))^{\frac{3}{2}}}}$$

With this formula it follows ($R_2 \ll R_1$):

$$v_{min} \approx \sqrt{\frac{Gm_p R_2 R_1 \cdot \cos \gamma}{R_1^3}} = \sqrt{\frac{Gm_p}{R_1^2} \cdot R_2 \cos \gamma}$$

Because $\frac{Gm_p}{R_1^2} = g =$ earth's acceleration, it is the same formula as in the homogeneous field.

In the case of a homogeneous field, the centrifugal force of the planet's rotation at the equator can easily be taken into consideration. We insert the term $g - R_1 \cdot w^2$ instead of g . w is the angular velocity of the planet. If

T is the rotation time of the planet, we have $w = \frac{2\pi}{T}$.

Bibliography:

- [1] Harald Schröder "The loop" Wissenschaft und Technik Verlag, Berlin, 2002